

Extending Emergence: Heuristics and Neural Networks within an Informational Substrate Framework

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Abstract

Building on a previously proposed framework [1], which showed that spacetime, gauge symmetries, and complexity can emerge from a discrete informational substrate, we advance a simpler, unified view where heuristics are not external constructs but arise organically from the same informational foundation. Neural networks, understood as self-organizing patterns within the substrate, learn to navigate complexity by developing internal heuristic strategies. These heuristics become intrinsic cognitive tools—emergent behaviors formed as the system adapts and optimizes its interpretation of patterns. By foregrounding information as the primal substrate and embedding heuristics as natural outcomes of its self-organization, we present a clean and holistic account of how observers, whether human or artificial, manage the combinatorial richness of emergent physical laws.

1 Introduction

In previous work [1], we established that fundamental structures like spacetime geometry, gauge symmetries [16, 17], black hole entropy [19], and complexity measures [2, 3, 4, 30] can arise from a discrete informational substrate—a lattice of fundamental degrees of freedom interacting locally. From

these simple building blocks, continuous laws, gravitational phenomena, and intricate entanglement patterns emerge.

However, as complexity builds, observers—whether biological, artificial, or otherwise—face the challenge of identifying relevant patterns, making predictions, and gaining understanding. Traditional theories often treat *heuristics* as external intellectual constructs, but here we argue that heuristics themselves are integral emergent features. More specifically, we show how neural network dynamics within the informational substrate naturally give rise to heuristics as adaptive shortcuts for complexity navigation.

2 Information as the Fundamental Substrate

2.1 Primal Medium

Our starting point is a four-dimensional lattice $\Lambda = \mathbb{Z}^4$ [5, 6, 7, 8, 9], populated by informational variables (bits, qubits, or more general degrees of freedom). Local update rules define how states evolve step-by-step [10]. Initially, there is no geometry, no symmetry, and no notion of scale. Yet, as correlations accumulate:

- **Spacetime Emerges:** Lorentz invariance and geometric concepts appear at large scales [1, 10, 11].
- **Gauge Symmetries and Holography:** Complex gauge structures and holographic dualities [14, 15] arise from pattern-encoded entanglement structures.
- **Complexity Measures:** Integrated information [2, 3, 4], black hole entropy [19], and other complexity metrics emerge naturally through combinatorial microstate counting.

All these phenomena unfold without imposing these features at the start—they materialize from the interplay of local rules and large-scale organization of information.

3 Neural Networks as Self-Organizing Dynamics

3.1 Formation Mechanisms

Neural networks are not artificially introduced; they spontaneously emerge as certain configurations of the informational substrate exploit feedback loops, memory effects, and pattern stabilization. Consider local clusters of variables that become self-referential: over time, these clusters develop feedback channels and reinforce correlations, eventually stabilizing into structures that process inputs and produce outputs—just as biological or artificial neural networks do [31, 30].

- **Local Interactions Lead to Global Patterns:** Neighboring nodes influence each other’s states, and iterative reinforcement of certain state transitions gives rise to stable network architectures.
- **Adaptive Refinement:** As these nascent networks *experience* different configurations, they adjust their internal link strengths (akin to synaptic weights), gradually improving their ability to predict or interpret the substrate’s state. This process parallels learning dynamics in artificial neural networks trained on complex datasets [31, 30].

4 Heuristics as Intrinsic Behavioral Tools

4.1 Adaptive Strategies from Complexity

Faced with a vast combinatorial landscape of possible states, neural networks must find efficient strategies to extract meaningful patterns. This necessity sparks the emergence of **heuristics**—internal shortcuts or rules-of-thumb that guide the network’s interpretation and decision-making processes.

- **Heuristics as Internal Filters:** Instead of brute-forcing every possibility, the network learns to focus on relevant subsets of variables or certain invariant features. For example, a neural network might develop a “zoom-out” heuristic to identify scale-invariant correlations that resemble geometric structures or a “zoom-in” heuristic to track localized, short-range interactions critical for predicting local events.

- **No External Input Required:** These heuristics are not imposed from outside. They are natural consequences of the network’s learning dynamics, arising as it tries to maximize predictive accuracy, minimize unnecessary complexity, or stabilize internal representations.

5 Illustrative Examples

5.1 Conceptual Scenario

Consider a simplified lattice Ising model [9] with spins up or down. Initially, the network embedded in this substrate has no strategy. Over repeated exposure, it notices that large-scale magnetized regions form under certain temperatures. The network develops a heuristic: “Focus on aggregated local spins to guess global magnetization.” This is a rudimentary example of extracting a global pattern from local data.

5.2 Simulated AI Environment

In computational experiments, we can embed artificial agents (modeled as neural networks) within a substrate that simulates emergent laws. These agents, starting with no prior knowledge, learn to predict macroscopic variables (e.g., effective “fields,” emergent symmetries). Over training, the agent’s hidden units form heuristics: they ignore irrelevant fluctuations and highlight stable features that correlate with large-scale regularities, much like deep learning networks focusing on edges or shapes in image classification tasks [31, 30].

6 Connections to Real-World Systems

Biological brains offer a potent analogy. Through evolution and lifelong learning, brains form neural circuits that develop cognitive shortcuts. These heuristics—such as perceptual grouping or pattern completion—reduce the burden of processing an overwhelming sensory environment. Our framework suggests that the same principle operates at a fundamental level of information:

- **Evolutionary Time Scales:** Over evolutionary scales, biological brains discover shortcuts to handle complex ecological challenges. Similarly,

neural networks in the substrate discover stable patterns that help them navigate complexity.

- **Cognitive Processes:** Neural heuristics in brains and emergent heuristics in substrate-based networks share the principle of optimizing information handling, reflecting a universal strategy for dealing with complexity.

7 Implications for Fundamental Physics

7.1 Reframing the Observer

In traditional physics, observers and their cognitive tools often stand outside the formalism. Here, observers—human physicists or artificial agents—are themselves emergent neural networks within the informational substrate. Their heuristics, concepts, and frameworks are thus on the same ontological footing as spacetime and gauge fields.

- **Unification and Quantum Gravity:** If heuristics and interpretation strategies emerge endogenously, this may inform approaches to quantum gravity where the observer’s measurements and interpretive frameworks cannot be separated from the underlying quantum substrate [14, 15, 18].
- **Epistemic Limits and Undecidability:** Certain properties may remain undecidable or not fully knowable [1, 22]. The heuristics that emerge in networks represent stable, practical solutions that navigate, but do not eliminate, these epistemic limits.
- **Observational Role:** This viewpoint suggests that our entire scientific method—our ability to conceptualize and model physics—arises from the same substrate we study. It unifies observer and observed, making the search for a “theory of everything” also a theory of how such a theory can be discovered, represented, and understood.

8 Context-Dependent Heuristics

Heuristics are not one-size-fits-all. Depending on the environment, scale, and complexity:

- **Local Scale Heuristics:** In highly localized regimes, heuristics might focus on short-range interactions, tracking immediate cause-and-effect relationships, akin to local patch recognition.
- **Global Scale Abstractions:** In scenarios where large-scale patterns dominate, heuristics might compress information to a few order parameters or topological features, ignoring microscopic details and emphasizing global invariants.
- **Adaptive Switching:** As conditions change—e.g., temperature shifts in a lattice model or evolving boundary conditions—neural networks might dynamically switch between different heuristics, reflecting a context-dependent strategy for complexity reduction.

9 Conclusion

By recognizing that neural networks naturally form within the informational substrate and evolve heuristics as intrinsic strategies, we unify the entire narrative of emergence. Information is the bedrock, out of which space-time, symmetries, complexity, neural architectures, and heuristic methods co-emerge.

This perspective offers a streamlined understanding of how complexity is not only generated but also managed by the very structures it spawns. Heuristics are not artificially introduced; they reflect the substrate’s own solutions to complexity, made manifest through neural networks. The implications extend from understanding how we, as observers, conceptualize physics to guiding new approaches in artificial intelligence, simulations of quantum gravity, and interpretations of the observer’s role in a fundamentally informational universe.

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